

ETALON INTEGRALLAR

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Annotatsiya: Furye integrali uchun zarur bo‘lgan Erdey lemmasi va shu lemmaning tasdiqi isboti haqida.

Аннотация: О лемме Эрдей, необходимой для интеграла Фурье, и доказательстве утверждения этой леммы.

Annotation: About the Erdey lemma necessary for the Furye integral and the proof of confirmation of that lemma.

Quyidagi integralni qaraymiz

$$\Phi(\lambda) = \int_0^a x^{\beta-1} f(x) e^{i\lambda x^\alpha} dx. \quad (1)$$

1-Lemma. (Erdey lemmasi). Agar $\alpha \geq 1$, $\beta > 0$, $f(x) \in C^\infty([0, a])$ va $x=a$ nuqtada o‘zini hosilalari bilan birgalikda nolga aylansa. U holda

$$\int_0^a x^{\beta-1} f(x) e^{i\lambda x^\alpha} dx \sim \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a_k \lambda^{-\frac{k+\beta}{\alpha}} \quad (\lambda \rightarrow +\infty) \quad (2)$$

$$a_k = \frac{f^{(k)}(0)}{k! \alpha} \Gamma\left(\frac{k+\beta}{\alpha}\right) \exp\left[\frac{i\pi(k+\beta)}{2\alpha}\right]. \quad (3)$$

Bu yoyilmani λ bo‘yicha ixtiyoriy martta differensiallash mumkin.

Erdey lemmasi Furye integrali uchun shunday ro‘l o‘ynaydiki xuddi Vatson lemmasini Laplas integrallarida tutgan o‘rni kabi.

Isbot. $S = x^\alpha$ faza funktsiya yagona $x=0$ kritik nuqtaga ega integrallash sohasida.

Birinchi navbatda $0 \leq x \leq \delta$, bunda $0 < \delta < a$ da $f(x) \equiv 1$ bo‘ladi. U holda Integral ostidagi funktsiya $(0, \delta)$ da analitik funktsiya bo‘ladi. $0 < \arg x < \pi/\alpha$ sektorda biz quyidagiga ega bo‘lamiz $Re(ix^\alpha) < 0$. Koshi teoremasiga ko‘ra $[0, \frac{\delta}{2}]$ kesma bo‘yicha integral $l = l_1 \cup l_2$ bo‘yicha integralga teng bunda l_1 – kesma $[0, e^{\frac{i\pi}{2\alpha}\rho_0}]$, l_2 – kesma $[e^{\frac{i\pi}{2\alpha}\rho_0}, \delta/2]$. U holda

$$\Phi_\beta(\lambda) = \Phi_\beta^{(1)}(\lambda) + \Phi_\beta^{(2)}(\lambda) + \Phi_\beta^{(3)}(\lambda) \quad (4)$$

bunda quyidagiga ega bo‘lamiz

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_{\beta}^{(1)}(\lambda) &= \int_0^{e^{\frac{i\pi}{2\alpha}\rho_0}} x^{\beta} e^{i\lambda x^{\alpha}} dx = e^{\frac{i\pi(\beta+1)}{2\alpha}} \int_0^{\rho} x^{\beta} e^{-\lambda x^{\alpha}} dx = \\ &\alpha^{-1} \Gamma\left(\frac{\beta+1}{\alpha}\right) e^{\frac{i\pi(\beta+1)}{2\alpha}} \lambda^{-\frac{\beta+1}{\alpha}} + O(e^{-c\lambda}) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Vatson lemmasiga ko'ra . Bo'laklab integrallab , quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_{\beta}^{(2)}(\lambda) + \Phi_{\beta}^{(3)}(\lambda) &= \frac{x^{\beta} \exp(i\lambda x^{\alpha})}{i\alpha \lambda x^{\alpha-1}} \Big|_{\frac{i\pi}{e^{2\alpha}\rho_0}}^{\delta/2} - \\ &-(i\alpha\lambda)^{-1} \int_{l_2}^{\alpha} \exp(i\lambda x^{\alpha}) (x^{\beta-\alpha+1})' dx + (i\alpha\lambda x^{\alpha-1})^{-1} x^{\beta} f(x) \exp(i\lambda x^{\alpha}) \Big|_{\frac{\alpha}{\delta}}^{\alpha} - \\ &-(i\alpha\lambda)^{-1} \int_{\delta/2}^{\alpha} \exp(i\lambda x^{\alpha}) (f(x)x^{\beta-\alpha+1})' dx. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Bundan o'z-o'zidan (6) dagi integral ostidagi postanovka $O(\lambda^{-\infty})$ tartibga ega va bundan tashqari

$$\Phi_{\beta}^{(2)}(\lambda) + \Phi_{\beta}^{(3)}(\lambda) = O(\lambda^{-\infty}) \quad (\lambda \rightarrow +\infty) \quad (7)$$

$\lambda \geq 0$ da l_1, l_2, l_3 kesmalar bo'yicha $|\exp(i\lambda x^{\alpha})| \leq 1$ ekanligidan va $f'(x) \in C^{\infty}([0, a])$ va $0 \leq x \leq \delta$ da $f'(x) \equiv 0$ ekanligidan foydalansak. Quyidagiga kelamiz

$$\Phi_{\beta}^{(2)}(\lambda) + \Phi_{\beta}^{(3)}(\lambda) = \frac{\alpha-\beta}{i\lambda\alpha} [\Phi_{\beta-\alpha}^{(2)}(\lambda) + \Phi_{\beta-\alpha}^{(3)}(\lambda)] + O(\lambda^{-\infty}). \quad (8)$$

Bizdai (7) ga ko'ra $\Phi_{\beta}^{(2)}(\lambda) + \Phi_{\beta}^{(3)}(\lambda) = O(\lambda^{-1})$ va (8) ga ko'ra $\Phi_{\beta}^{(2)}(\lambda) + \Phi_{\beta}^{(3)}(\lambda) = O(\lambda^{-2})$ ga ega bo'lamiz bu jarayondi davom etirib quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz $\Phi_{\beta}^{(2)}(\lambda) + \Phi_{\beta}^{(3)}(\lambda) = O(\lambda^{-\infty})$ bu baholashdan va (4), (5) ga ko'ra quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz

$$\Phi_{\beta}(\lambda) = \alpha^{-1} \Gamma\left(\frac{\beta+1}{\alpha}\right) e^{\frac{i\pi(\beta+1)}{2\alpha}} \lambda^{-\frac{\beta+1}{\alpha}} + O(\lambda^{-\infty}) \quad (\lambda \rightarrow +\infty) \quad (9)$$

Agar kichik x larda $f(x) \equiv 1$ bo'lsa. Lemmani umumiy holatda Teylor Formulasiga ko'ra isbot qilamiz

2-Lemma. Erdey lemmasidagi tasdiq o'rinli $|\lambda| \rightarrow \infty, 0 \leq \arg \lambda \leq \pi$ bo'lganda xuddi shunday $\arg \lambda$ bo'yicha ham.

Isbot. Agar $\varepsilon \leq \theta = \arg \lambda \leq \pi - \varepsilon$, bunda $0 < \varepsilon < \pi$ unda (1) integral Vatson lemmasini shartlarini bajaradi . shuning uchun quyidagini isbotlasak yetarli (2) asimptotikasi uchun quyidagi o'rinli $0 \leq \theta \leq \varepsilon, \pi - \varepsilon \leq \theta \leq \pi$ sektorlarda qayerdagi $\varepsilon > 0$ ni ixtiyoriyicha kichik tanlash mumkin. Agar $0 \leq \theta \leq \varepsilon$ u holda $0 \leq \arg x \leq \pi/2\alpha$ sektorda quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz

$$\operatorname{Re}(i\lambda x^{\alpha}) = -|\lambda||x^{\alpha}| \sin(\theta + \alpha \arg x) \leq 0$$

Bunda albatda $0 \leq \theta + \alpha \arg x \leq \frac{\pi}{2\alpha} + \varepsilon$ ekanligini hisobga oldik. O‘z-o‘zidan l_1, l_2, l_3 kesmalar bo‘yicha $|\exp(i\lambda x^\alpha)| \leq 1$ va yuqoridagi lemma isbotida qurilgan narsalar to‘liq $0 \leq \theta \leq \varepsilon$ holat uchun ko‘chiriladi. Analitik ravishda $\pi - \varepsilon \leq \theta \leq \pi$ ga ham.

Misol 1. $\lambda \rightarrow +\infty$ bo‘lganda quyidagi munosabat o‘rinli ekanligini isbotlang

$$\int_0^1 \exp(i\lambda x^3) dx \sim \Gamma\left(\frac{4}{3}\right) e^{\frac{i\pi}{6}} \lambda^{-\frac{1}{3}} - \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(k + \frac{2}{3})}{\Gamma(-\frac{1}{3})} (i\lambda)^{-k-1} e^{i\lambda}.$$

Erdey tomonidan 1-lemmani boshqacharoq isboti keltirilgan va biz uni keltiramiz sababi u bazi foydali texnik ozgarishlar ega . $\alpha \geq 1, 0 < \beta \leq 1$ bo‘lsin,

$\Phi_\beta(\lambda)$ ni quyidagicha ko‘rinishda keltiramiz :

$$\Phi_\beta(\lambda) = \int_0^\alpha f(x) d\left(\int_\infty^x t^{\beta-1} e^{i\lambda t^\alpha} dt\right)$$

va bo‘laklab integrallaymiz . bunda integral quyidagi o‘q bo‘yicha olinayabdi

$l_t: t = x + \rho e^{\frac{i\pi}{2\alpha}}, \rho > 0, t$ kompleks tekislikdan. N marta bo‘laklab integrallab quyidagiga ega bo‘lamiz

$$\Phi_\beta(\lambda) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} (-1)^n f^{(n)}(0) \varphi_{-n-1}(0, \lambda) + R_N(\lambda),$$

$$R_N(\lambda) = (-1)^{N+1} \int_0^\alpha \varphi_{-N}(x, \lambda) f^N(x) dx \quad (10)$$

Bu yerda quyidagicha aniqlangan

$$\varphi_{-n-1}(x, \lambda) = \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{n!} \int_{l_x} (t-x)^n t^{\beta-1} \exp(i\lambda t^\alpha) dt \quad (11)$$

(10) dagi yig‘indi boshlang‘ich N elementini baholshga imkon beradi. Bundan quyidagi natijaga kelamiz

$$|R_N(\lambda)| \leq C_N \lambda^{-\frac{N}{\alpha}} \int_0^\alpha x^{\beta-1} dx = C'_N \lambda^{-\frac{N}{\alpha}} \quad (12)$$

Bunda N ixtiyoriy ekanligidan yuqoridagi munosabat isbot bo‘ldi.

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